

100 Households, 100 Circular Stories: Inspiring Sustainable Living in Europe

Deliverable 4.3: Methodological framework and strategy for workshops and engagement with stakeholders

Delivery year: 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101135495.

UK participants in Horizon Europe Project CircleUp are supported by UKRI grant numbers: 10115495 Oxfordshire County Council and 10110987 Earthwatch Europe.

Document information

Project number	101135495		Project acronym	CircleUp
Full project title	100 Households, 100 Circular Stories: Inspiring Sustainable Living in Europe			
Project URL	circle-up.eu			
EU project adviser	Erik Pentimalli			
Deliverable number	D4.3	Title	D4.3 – Methodological framework and strategy for workshops and engagement with stakeholders	
Work package number	WP4	Title	Piloting projects	
Date of delivery	Contractual	Month 09	Actual	Month 09
		September 2025		September 2025
Dissemination level	PU – Public			
Lead partner	Prosperkolleg e.V.			
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Keywords	Circular economy transition; stakeholder engagement; local context			

Version log			
Version as date	Author	Partner	Change or comments

To cite this document:

Beitz, B.; Trost, E.; Irrek, W.; Burns, R.; Watson, M; Verachtert, S. (2025). D4.3. Methodological framework and strategy for workshops and engagement with stakeholders. Deliverable report of Horizon Europe project CircleUp (grant agreement No 101135495).

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full text
CE	Circular Economy
D#.#	A deliverable of a project
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
WP	Work package

Executive summary

This document details the strategy for engaging stakeholders in the CircleUp project. Recognizing that consumer habits are shaped by their local environment, i.e. the availability of infrastructure, our project goes beyond individual interventions to address systemic barriers to circular practices, such as a lack of accessible repair services or limited options for reusable packaging. Our approach is designed to facilitate a participatory exchange with stakeholders to build a supportive environment for households.

The core of our strategy is a flexible, five-stage process. We provide our consortium partners with guidelines on how to implement the framework in their respective local contexts, while giving them the autonomy to adapt their approach as required. We prioritise stakeholders using an Interest/Influence Matrix, focusing on those who are most critical to the project's success, such as local community leaders and small businesses. All communication is guided by a core storyline that portrays the project as a positive, collaborative effort. All materials will be tailored to resonate with the local audience.

Throughout the project, stakeholder involvement will evolve from networking and recruitment to potential collaboration and, finally, dissemination. We will use workshops as a key mechanism for generating ideas and facilitating a participatory exchange. To ensure our strategy remains effective, we will evaluate stakeholder activities by administering questionnaires and conducting optional interviews with selected stakeholders. This will provide us with crucial feedback on how our interventions are received, enabling us to make any necessary adjustments. Through this strategy, stakeholders are positioned as active participants in a shared learning process, helping to test and refine a framework for a more circular way of life.

1. Introduction

Consumer behaviour occurs within systems comprising infrastructure, social structures and structured spaces. It can only be understood, when this structural embeddedness is considered. Consumers – or citizens – are situated within a physical environment that provides resources and barriers for circular behaviour. These “spatial arrangements” of infrastructure within a city or neighbourhood refer to the way physical spaces are organised and used in everyday life, for example the way people buy, prepare and consume food (Baur 2023). Food-related activities are, i.e., closely interwoven with other daily routines such as commuting to work, childcare responsibilities, and running errands, all of which are distributed across various locations within the urban space. Such activities are highly habitualised: Once routines are established, they tend to be repeated automatically and are resistant to change (Verplanken 2006) even when more sustainable alternatives are – or become – available.

Interventions promoting circular behaviours must acknowledge a key challenge: the spatial and social contexts in which individuals operate. In many cities and neighbourhoods, the availability of sustainable options – such as repair shops, second-hand stores, or recycling facilities – may not align with people's established daily routines. When these alternatives are not easily accessible or are not part of the routines in daily life, they are less likely to be adopted, thereby limiting the uptake of circular practices.

Furthermore, a lack of available sustainable options can itself be a major barrier. In such cases, the shift to more sustainable lifestyles requires more than just individual effort. It calls for a collective process where citizens are recognised not as passive consumers but as active participants with the power to shape their local environment (Schulte et al. 2020). This involves citizens identifying structural barriers they face and then, through collaboration, developing their own local solutions or initiating bottom-up activities to fill those gaps.

Our project is designed to address two key challenges arising from this reality. First, we need to effectively understand the local structures that influence whether households can adopt circular behaviours. By understanding these structures, we can provide households with the necessary orientation, showing them where circular options are located within their city and how to adapt their routines to align with Circular Economy goals. Our answer to this challenge is the CircleUp household intervention, which includes an online platform dedicated to collecting local Circular Economy (CE) resources and identifying places to consume in a more circular way.

Secondly, recognizing the need for a collective process, we aim to facilitate an exchange that empowers citizens in their respective roles as stakeholders – such as professionals, entrepreneurs, and local actors within SMEs – to take the first steps toward building a more circular community. This collective aspect is woven into the very fabric of the project through our community building approach, outlined in detail in Deliverable 2.1. By combining this with the stakeholder engagement concept provided in this document, CircleUp will help individuals to connect, share insights, and co-develop solutions from the ground up.

2. Framework for working with stakeholders

A viable approach to understand – and potentially partly shape – the local structures, in which consumers act every day, is to involve the stakeholder landscape, and particularly those who have an interest in the project’s goal to start a transformative process towards Circular Economy. The CircleUp project’s primary objective is to increase the adoption of circular practices at the household level. While the behavioural intervention package (see D2.1) is directed at individuals and their social networks, the project acknowledges that households do not exist in a vacuum. The successful uptake and long-term sustainability of circular behaviours depend on a supportive ecosystem of local stakeholders. Therefore, a robust and structured approach for engaging these stakeholders is essential to the project’s success.

Drawing from the five-stage stakeholder engagement methodology of Conway et al. (2024), in which they present a methodology for stakeholder engagement as a clear, five-stage process (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**), we will facilitate a collaborative process to co-create solutions. This framework recognizes that a systemic shift to a circular economy requires collaboration between all key stakeholders, from citizens and local businesses to civil society organizations and policymakers.

Figure 1: Five-Step Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (Conway et al. 2024), Open Res Europe 2024

The following sections describe how we will implement the Conway et al. (2024) framework for CircleUp.

Stage 1: Internal Participatory Planning

This foundational stage ensures that the stakeholder engagement strategy is a collective effort, drawing on the diverse knowledge and experiences of the CircleUp consortium partners. Through internal collaborative sessions and discussions, we will establish a set of harmonized principles and a shared process for stakeholder identification and data management, aligning with GDPR guidelines. While the consortium will agree on core guidelines and inclusion exclusion criteria (see section 2.1), each partner will maintain the

autonomy to build on existing connections and leverage their local expertise. This allows for adequate **adaptation to local situations and tailoring stakeholder work to local needs**. Tailoring may for example be needed regarding communication channels, developing events and workshops or regarding the number and type of stakeholders involved. This ensures the stakeholder selection and engagement process is highly responsive to the unique cultural and structural contexts of each of the four case study countries, allowing for effective, country-specific approaches.

Table 1 displays the partners responsible for local implementation within each case study:

Table 1: Responsible partners for stakeholder involvement within in the different countries

Case study	Germany	Latvia	Norway	UK
Responsible partner	Prosperkolleg e.V.	Latvian Rural Forum	Friends of the Earth Norway	Oxford County Council
Supported by	VZ NRW, HRW	RTU	NTNU	Earthwatch

Stage 2: Stakeholder Identification and Mapping

The consortium partners will identify and map relevant stakeholders at the local level. This will involve an inclusive and comprehensive process to identify key individuals and organizations. By mobilizing the diverse networks of the consortium, we will identify stakeholders with the capacity and common interests to support CircleUp. This process will also emphasize reaching “harder to access” but highly interested groups, such as small-scale businesses or local community leaders, who are often critical to on-the-ground change.

Stage 3: Stakeholder Analysis and Prioritisation

Once identified, stakeholders will be analysed and categorised based on their level of interest and potential influence on the project's outcomes. This will involve each partner independently conducting an internal analysis using an Interest/Influence Matrix to segment stakeholders into priority groups (Figure 2). Influence can be defined in line with the Conway et al. as stakeholders “ability to influence project actions, outcomes and reputation”.

Figure 2: Stakeholder interest/influence matrix (Conway et al. 2024), Open Res Europe 2024

This analysis will provide a strategic foundation by creating a clear roadmap for our engagement efforts. Instead of a one-size-fits-all approach, it allows each partner to prioritize their actions based on each stakeholder's potential to impact the project. As CircleUp focuses on a bottom-up approach to circularity in four material flows – food, textiles, packaging, and electronics – our stakeholder analysis will be highly tailored to this context. Each identified stakeholder will be placed within one of the four quadrants of the matrix based on their potential to influence the project and their level of interest in its outcomes:

- **Key stakeholders (high influence, high interest):** This group is critical for a project focused on local, community-level change. In this context, we understand influence as a stakeholder's capacity to directly affect project actions, outcomes, and reputation at the local level. This can include local community leaders, respected small business owners (e.g., a well-known tailor or a popular second-hand shop), and proactive municipal officials. Their influence comes from their on-the-ground credibility, their networks, and their capacity to directly provide the circular services that the project's participants will need. These stakeholders will be engaged closely and consistently.
- **Interested stakeholders (low influence, high interest):** This is a vital group for CircleUp, as it includes local community groups, engaged individuals, and participants themselves. While they may not have broad systemic influence, their high interest and on-the-ground presence are essential for providing practical circular solutions to households. The strategy will focus on empowering and supporting them, building their capacity, and keeping them well-informed.
- **Influential stakeholders (high influence, low interest):** These stakeholders have the ability to affect the project's reputation or scale, even if their direct interest is low. This group could include large, national retailers or influential local media outlets. The strategy will focus on raising their awareness and demonstrating the project's value to them, thereby encouraging their participation and ensuring their influence is not a negative factor.
- **Passive Stakeholders (low influence, low interest):** This group is of limited importance to the project's core objectives. They will not be monitored.

This tailored analysis ensures that our resources are focused on the stakeholders who are most critical to the project's success, while also empowering those who are most passionate about the circular economy.

Stage 4: Engagement and Co-Creation

This stage is the core of our strategy, where we actively involve stakeholders through targeted activities. Key activities will include participatory workshops, dedicated communication channels, and eventually opportunities for stakeholders to directly engage with participants via the project's digital platform. The goal is to facilitate a two-way exchange, allowing stakeholders to design and offer their own circular products and services – from repair café vouchers and second-hand discounts to educational workshops – that directly support and reinforce the behavioural changes sought by the project. This stage is crucial for building trust and a sense of shared ownership.

A more detailed description of the stakeholder workshops can be found in section 3.3.

Stage 5: Continuous Evaluation and Feedback

The stakeholder activities are designed to serve as a crucial feedback mechanism for the project. We will evaluate their effectiveness through a combination of quantitative questionnaires (see appendix) distributed after the workshops and by observing their activities and input on the digital platform. This feedback will contribute to our understanding of how our intervention is being received by key local actors.

2.1 Definition, inclusion and exclusion criteria

For the purpose of the CircleUp project, we define stakeholders broadly in line with Conway et al. (2024) as any individual, group, or organization that can be affected by the project or that can affect its actions, outcomes, and reputation. Our selection of stakeholders is guided by their local relevance and their alignment with the project's core objectives, ensuring that we engage a diverse and impactful group of actors.

Inclusion Criteria

We identify CircleUp stakeholders as local groups, initiatives, associations, non-profit or municipal organizations, retailers, or service providers that meet at least one the following criteria:

- **Aligned with Circular Economy Principles:** They have already aligned their activities, either fully or partially, with the principles of the Circular Economy. The CE principles we refer to are outlined in D2.1.
- **Demonstrated Interest:** They express a clear and deep interest in the Circular Economy and plan to align at least part of their activities with its principles within the project's timeframe.
- **Educational or Artistic Contribution:** They offer educational or artistic programs related to the Circular Economy.

The final selection of stakeholders will mirror the project's focus on four key material streams by including entities with a direct or indirect linkage to textiles, food, electronics, and packaging.

In addition to the defined stakeholder groups, the local press – including newspapers, online news platforms, and radio – will be considered a meta-stakeholder. This is due to their unique capacity to influence project outcomes and reputation by shaping public opinion, influencing other stakeholders' perceptions, and amplifying key project developments and success stories through media coverage.

Exclusion Criteria

To ensure the project's integrity and genuine commitment to its values, we have established the following exclusion criteria:

- **Non-Adherence to values of human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality and human rights:** Stakeholders must adhere to and respect foundational human rights, as for example outlined in Article 2 of the Treaty on the European Union (2012). This includes respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities. While constructive criticism of specific EU policies is acceptable, any open rejection of EU democratic principles is considered incompatible with the project's values and will result in exclusion from engagement.
- **Greenwashing Practices:** The CircleUp project is committed to integrity. While a comprehensive, pre-emptive screening is not within the scope of our work, any stakeholder can be excluded should verifiable complaints or new information arise concerning greenwashing or unethical behaviour. In such cases, our team will conduct targeted research to determine if exclusion is warranted. The decision to exclude the stakeholder will be made jointly by the respective local consortium partner and the project coordinator.

2.2 Stakeholder groups

To facilitate the engagement of the CircleUp participants and strengthen the local CE resources and awareness, we aim to collaborate with stakeholders in the following five areas:

1. Public and Civil Society Actors

This group includes all governmental bodies, non-profit organizations (NGOs), and citizen-led initiatives that shape public policy, advocate for environmental change, or mobilize communities. Their support is critical for broad dissemination, policy alignment, and fostering bottom-up engagement.

- Examples: City and district administration offices, local public relations departments, environmental NGOs, and food-sharing initiatives.

2. Commercial and Retail Partners

This category includes businesses and market-based actors that provide circular goods and services. Their involvement is essential for offering tangible opportunities for circular consumption, such as second-hand goods, repair services, or zero-waste options.

- Examples: Second-hand shops, weekly markets, local repair services, bakeries, and clothing alteration businesses.

3. Educational and Research Institutions

This group consists of organizations and institutions that contribute to knowledge, capacity building, and public awareness. Their role is to provide workshops, educational programs, and research insights that help legitimize and popularize the circular economy.

- Examples: Universities, adult education centres, and environmental education stations.

4. Media and Dissemination Channels

These are the communication platforms and outlets that can amplify the project's message and reach a broader audience. Their ability to influence public opinion and disseminate information is crucial for recruitment and scaling the project's impact.

- Examples: Local newspapers, community news platforms, and city-focused social media channels.

5. Creative and Community Spaces

This category includes cultural institutions and informal community spaces. These stakeholders are vital for making the circular economy relatable and tangible. They can act as "resonance spaces", providing a creative platform for new ideas, and helping to weave circularity into the cultural fabric of a city.

- Examples: Theatres, art collectives, and open project spaces.

2.3 Purpose to involve stakeholders in the project's lifecycle

The local stakeholder's diverse perspectives and expertise are vital for enriching the local pilots and ensuring the project's interventions are grounded in the realities of each case study. Ultimately, stakeholders are essential for increasing the project's impact and scaling up CE practices through their professional roles, community involvement, and communication channels.

In concrete terms, stakeholders exert their influence on the project through several key mechanisms:

- **Providing infrastructure and services:** Stakeholders can influence project actions by providing essential infrastructure for circular practices. This includes offering spaces or opportunities for buying, selling, exchanging, repairing, or sharing goods.
- **Co-creation and participation:** By participating in and co-creating local workshops and events, stakeholders may directly influence the project's core activities and outcomes, ensuring they are relevant and well-supported.
- **Creative and strategic input:** Stakeholders can influence project outcomes by generating ideas, providing feedback, and offering resonance spaces (e.g., in theatres or art collectives), which help to shape the project's narrative and foster broader community engagement.
- **Dissemination and upscaling:** Stakeholders are crucial for influencing the project's reputation and reach. They act as vital channels for disseminating information within their networks, particularly from hard-to-reach groups, where their local credibility serves as a "door opener."

Stakeholder engagement in CircleUp is a dynamic process. Its specific purpose and the nature of stakeholder contributions evolve in different project phases, aligning with the project's changing needs from recruitment to dissemination, as outlined in Table 2.

Table 2: Purpose for stakeholder involvement within different project phases

Timeframe	July – December 2025	January – December 2026	January – December 2027
Focus	Networking, inspiration and recruitment	Opportunities for circular consumption	Feedback, dissemination, upscaling
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project presentation • getting to know stakeholders • Inspire them to contribute to in CircleUp, i.e. through offering space, education or services • Reach possible participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input for challenges (as outlined in D2.1), e.g. in experimental learning tasks • Extend opportunities for circular consumption for participants • Facilitate exchange between stakeholders and households 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate learnings of stakeholder work • Disseminate project results via stakeholder networks • Encourage uptake of project results for future activities

3. Process of stakeholder involvement

Effective stakeholder involvement is crucial for CircleUp, but given that resource constraints often limit the capacity of key stakeholders, particularly non-profits and smaller initiatives, a structured process is essential to ensure that their participation is streamlined, valuable, and consistent throughout the project.

3.1 Timeline

Our stakeholder engagement strategy follows a comprehensive, five-stage process adapted from Conway et al. (2024), as outlined in in section 2 Framework for working with stakeholders. It is designed to be **flexible and iterative**, allowing for continuous adaptation and improvement throughout the project's lifecycle.

Table 3 provides an overview of the three phases of the stakeholder engagement strategy across the project's lifespan. Phase 1 (July–December 2025) is dedicated to recruitment and initial setup, involving the research and contact of relevant local stakeholders, outlining the communication strategy, and setting up the first stakeholder workshop to support the CircleUp challenges in the first intervention phase. The main output is a table of local stakeholders, consent forms, the documentation and feedback of the workshop and a preliminary list of planned stakeholder activities for the first intervention phase. Next, Phase 2 (January–December 2026) centers on supporting and integrating stakeholder initiatives. This includes populating the CircleUp Knowledge Base with stakeholder data and facilitating the second stakeholder workshop. This workshop's main goal is to encourage stakeholders to offer or co-design circular opportunities for the project's second intervention phase. The main output is the implementation of stakeholder data in CircleUp's knowledge platform, a list of local circular opportunities for the second intervention phase, together with documentation of the workshop and feedback from the stakeholders. Finally, Phase 3 (January–December 2027) focuses on feedback, dissemination, and upscaling, with the goal of motivating stakeholders to integrate and spread the project's results, resulting in 1–3 stakeholders taking up results for further, independent activity.

Table 3: Stakeholder activities and output in different project phases

Phase	Timeframe	Main focus	Measures/ activities	Output
1	July – December 2025	<p>Stages 1-3: Networking Stakeholder & participant recruitment</p> <p>Stage 4-5: Supporting challenges</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research relevant local stakeholders - Decide on communication strategy - Get into contact with stakeholders - Encourage stakeholders to get involved in project - Facilitate first stakeholder workshop - Ask stakeholders to fill in survey (see appendix) - Support stakeholders in integrating and potentially expanding their existing circular initiatives to address the challenges of the first intervention phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Table with local stakeholders - Project presentation in local language - Informed consent form in local language - Surveys in local language - Workshop summary documentation, including a list of activities and circular opportunities planned by stakeholders for first intervention phase - Survey data

2	January – December 2026	Stage 4-5: Supporting challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate stakeholder input in digital platform - Facilitate exchange between stakeholders and households (i.e. in first participant event) - Encourage households' participation in stakeholder activities and offers - Facilitate second stakeholder workshop, possibly encouraging stakeholders to co-design challenges or to design or integrate circular opportunities for the second intervention phase - Getting feedback from stakeholders from brief questionnaire together with informal feedback in personal discussions (optional) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge platform filled with stakeholder information - Stakeholder participation in participants' event - Workshop summary documentation, including a list of challenges, CE opportunities, activities and offers, co-designed or planned by stakeholders for the 2nd intervention phase - Survey data
3	January – December 2027	Stage 5: Feedback Dissemination Upscaling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate project results among stakeholders - Motivate stakeholders to spread project results via their communication channels - Activate stakeholders to take up project results for their own future activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1-3 stakeholders taking up results for further activity

The commitment to flexibility and iterative development is central to our engagement strategy. This means that three phases as outlined in Table 3 are not treated as rigid, isolated blocks. Instead, the process is designed for continuous adaptation. The timelines are viewed as guidance, allowing the project partners to accommodate necessary adjustments, such as extending recruitment or communication efforts, across phases. Furthermore, every activity, including the initial stakeholder list from Phase 1, is subject to refinement and improvement as insights are gathered in later stages.

During the development of the stakeholder framework, the necessity of holding workshops versus relying on bilateral communication was raised by several partners. Reflecting the flexible and tailored nature of our overall strategy, implementing partners may utilize alternative engagement means if they can demonstrate a sound rationale that achieves the project's core objectives for that specific case study. For example, if a pilot area already has a strong CE ecosystem, the stakeholder strategy does not need to focus on building the network from scratch, but on optimizing, connecting, and leveraging the existing strengths. Also, with a strong existing network, efforts may be better spent on targeted bilateral communication.

Both workshops and bilateral communication serve valuable, complementary functions. While bilateral communication is crucial for personalised recruitment, addressing specific stakeholder concerns, and targeted follow-up on individual initiatives, workshops uniquely enable the cross-sectoral synergy and collective ideation often required for building a robust local circular economy ecosystem. Given the need for local flexibility, the strategy prioritizes the core objective of active stakeholder involvement. Implementing partners are therefore empowered to utilize the most effective engagement means for their specific case study, provided they establish a clear rationale that achieves this essential goal.

3.2 Communication

Effective communication is crucial to our stakeholder engagement strategy. To inspire active involvement, we will introduce the project in a way that resonates with each stakeholder. Our approach is based on a unifying framework, but implementing partners have the flexibility to adapt communication channels and messaging to their local context.

Key benefits for stakeholders

By joining CircleUp, stakeholders gain a meaningful opportunity to get involved into a local circular economy initiative and become part of an innovative European network. Their engagement offers several key benefits:

- **Visibility:** The project highlights the contributions of local partners and stakeholders through communication channels, events, and publications. This enhances their public profile and showcases their commitment to a circular economy.
- **Networking:** Stakeholders can connect with like-minded actors, enabling a valuable exchange of knowledge and ideas that strengthens the local CE ecosystem.
- **Co-creation opportunities:** CircleUp provides a unique platform to test and develop ideas, services, and formats in direct collaboration with researchers and practitioners, accelerating innovation.
- **Capacity building:** Through ongoing dialogue with local partners and project participants, stakeholders can deepen their expertise in circular practices and community engagement. This early involvement in the transition also builds their capacity to adapt to changing social and environmental conditions. It may potentially strengthen local networks for resource sharing and service provision, thereby increasing the collective resilience and long-term viability of the local circular economy.
- **Reputation and impact:** By contributing to CircleUp, stakeholders play a direct role in a meaningful transformation, helping to shape more sustainable local systems with lasting social and environmental benefits. This engagement can also strengthen internal culture, as employees gain a sense of purpose and pride from working for an organization that is visibly committed to positive change.

Balancing commercial engagement and project integrity

We recognize that achieving a systemic shift requires the involvement of commercial actors; however, in working with these entities, we carefully balance their individual commercial interests with the project's broader, non-competitive, and public-facing objectives. Furthermore, participation is contingent upon adherence to the established 'Exclusion Criteria' (see section 2.1), ensuring all engaged partners maintain the necessary ethical and value-based alignment with the project.

Since all stakeholders active in the field of CE will have the opportunity to participate, making the stakeholders visible in the CircleUp platform will not distort competition.

Commitment to accessible language

To maximize engagement and ensure broad appeal, a core principle of our communication strategy is the use of accessible, non-academic language in all materials prepared for stakeholders and the public. We will consciously translate project-specific terminology and scientific concepts into clear, action-oriented messaging to ensure relevance and easy uptake by all local partners.

3.2.1 Strategic communication for engagement

Effective communication is the cornerstone of our engagement and co-creation efforts (Stage 4). The primary goal is to not only introduce the CircleUp project to local stakeholders but also to inspire their active involvement. Our approach acknowledges that the most successful communication is highly tailored to each case study, drawing from the insights gained during **Stage 2: Stakeholder Identification and Mapping**. While a core framework is provided, implementing partners have the flexibility to adapt their communication channels and messaging to the local environment.

All local communication will be guided by these core principles:

- **Understanding the local landscape:** It is vital to take into account existing Circular Economy initiatives and key players in the case study area early on. This is not just about identifying stakeholders; it is about building on what is already in place. For instance, if a local community already runs a cloth swap event, our communication should highlight how we can expand its reach through our project.
- **Selecting the right channels:** The most effective communication channels will vary depending on the local demographic and cultural context. Partners will choose channels that align with their target audience's habits, such as specific social media platforms, local newspapers, or professional networks. This ensures that the message reaches the intended audience in the most efficient way possible.
- **Creating value-driven materials:** We recognize that stakeholders are busy. Therefore, our information materials must be concise and compelling, clearly outlining what CircleUp is about and, most importantly, the tangible benefits of their involvement. Communication will proactively highlight the immediate value and long-term impact they can expect from participating in the project.
- **Sustaining engagement:** Keeping stakeholders engaged throughout the project's lifecycle is a significant challenge addressed in this stage. Building strong, lasting relationships is key and can be achieved by:
 - Fostering relationships from the early project phases.
 - Empowering by providing them with the flexibility to shape their own contributions in a way that aligns with their interests.
 - Sharing relevant project updates and outcomes to maintain interest and momentum, with a specific focus on communicating benefits and results from their country and others.

3.2.2 Knowledge base to enhance visibility of stakeholders

The CircleUp “Knowledge Base”, which will be further defined D3.3, features an interactive map highlighting places and initiatives that support the circular economy and citizen-led initiatives within local neighbourhoods. Initially, the map will be equipped with local circular resources, which include local stakeholders.

Figure 3: Knowledge Base mock-up of Bottrop pilot

Figure 3 provides a fictional example of a dynamic map interface, visually representing the CE ecosystem within the city of Bottrop. It showcases the geographic distribution of CE initiatives and businesses, alongside with user-generated "Circular Stories". This illustration demonstrates how the digital platform facilitates the discovery of spatial CE resources. Clicking on the icons will provide details of the specific location or initiative, e.g. a short description, opening hours and a link to the website. Finally, filters will be available to enable users to sort locations by category.

Figure 3 All functionalities are strategically designed to connect households with their local environment and each other. By showcasing CE resources in their surroundings and facilitating the sharing of experiences, the interactive map helps to overcome a significant barrier to adoption – the lack of perceived accessibility.

While stakeholder networking is primarily driven by the workshops and in-person events, the platform serves a crucial, complementary role by acting as a digital hub that provides continuous visibility and connection points to sustain and expand those relationships between events. Its design ensures that the benefits to stakeholders are a direct result of their active contribution to a public good:

- **Enhancing visibility within a public resource:** The interactive map functions as a community-driven directory. By being listed on the map, stakeholders (e.g., repair shops, second-hand stores, zero-waste shops) gain direct visibility to a highly motivated audience of project participants actively seeking circular resources.
- **Fostering trust and credibility:** The *Circular Stories feature* allows stakeholders to be at the centre of a positive, narrative-driven experience. When a participant publicly shares a story about a great experience at a local repair shop or second-hand store, this might serve as a positive word-of-mouth reference that builds trust and enhances the stakeholder's reputation as a key local contributor to the circular economy.
- **Networking:** The platform serves as a hub where stakeholders can see other local actors, initiatives, and businesses. This fosters a sense of a shared community and can facilitate new collaborations or partnerships that might not have occurred otherwise.
- **Direct Engagement:** The interactive nature of the map potentially allows for a two-way exchange, giving stakeholders a direct channel to engage with the public and receive feedback.

Process of filling the Knowledge Base

The process of populating the Knowledge Base begins with proactively seeking permission from identified stakeholders to be added, which may serve as an initial engagement "icebreaker". Throughout the intervention phases, the resource grows dynamically through collaborative contribution: both participants and stakeholders can suggest new additions or adaptation of existing information. Technically, this may be managed for stakeholders either by suggesting additions for administrative moderation or by granting them direct access to their location via a personalised link.

Knowledge Base enrichment: Embedding of Circular Stories under review

The knowledge base might be further enriched by the project's Circular Stories feature, detailed in D2.1. Circular Stories are user-generated narratives about CE practices that allow users to publish personal stories connected to a challenge. We are currently discussing whether these stories can also be linked to specific places on the interactive map. This linkage would enable participants to discover and learn from others' experiences with local circular initiatives, whether they are associated with stakeholders or community services like a free-exchange shelf. This functionality is intended to add a human dimension to the geographical data, enabling users to explore personal experiences associated with different locations. Users would also be enabled to read and share stories associated with that location.

Clarification on digital engagement and General Data Protection Regulation

The "engagement" facilitated by the platform serves as a means for stakeholders to receive public feedback and questions on their listed initiatives (e.g., through public comments on stories or locations). It is not designed to include private, direct messaging between users and stakeholders, thereby simplifying GDPR compliance and mitigating risks associated with unsolicited contact. Stakeholders will generally not be granted direct administrative access to the platform; rather, they will interact with the Knowledge Base at a publicly accessible level, or at a level defined by their eventual user status, ensuring the project maintains oversight of data and content integrity.

3.2.3 A general storyline

The message used to approach potential stakeholders should be tailored to their specific interests – a zero-waste non-profit will respond to a different message than a local business. However, a general storyline that can be adapted across a wide range of stakeholders might be:

"The global economy is facing unprecedented challenges from resource scarcity. Our city/region is proactively preparing for a resilient and sustainable future by embracing the circular economy – a model where resources are used repeatedly, and products are designed for durability and easy reuse. Your organization can play a pivotal role in this transformative journey. We believe your expertise and network are invaluable in helping us inspire and support households to adopt circular practices in their daily lives. By collaborating with us, your ideas, work, and network can make a real difference."

This narrative is designed to be highly effective by:

- **Establishing a shared challenge:** It begins by acknowledging a universal problem (resource scarcity), which establishes the project's broad relevance.
- **Creating a positive vision:** It frames the local response as a proactive, forward-looking solution, positioning the project as a positive force for change.

- **Empowering the stakeholder:** It directly appeals to the stakeholder's expertise and role, making it clear that their unique contributions are not just welcome but are essential for the project's success.
- **Providing a clear call to action:** It defines a tangible role for the stakeholder—helping to inspire and support local households—which provides a clear reason for them to get involved and highlights the immediate value of their participation.

This core storyline will be the foundation upon which all local communication is built, ensuring consistency while allowing for the necessary flexibility to appeal to a diverse range of stakeholders.

3.3 Organisation of workshops and events

Workshops and events are a core component of the CircleUp project's stakeholder engagement strategy. They serve as a key mechanism within **Stage 4: Engagement and co-creation**, providing a platform for direct exchange, fostering networking, and generating innovative ideas. At least two key stakeholder events are planned to align with the project's intervention phases, ensuring that stakeholders are actively involved in the co-creation and implementation of project activities.

3.3.1 First stakeholder workshop: Networking and idea generation

Recognizing the autonomy of each consortium partner, the initial outreach and communication phase is scheduled for September-October 2025. Following this, each partner can schedule their first stakeholder workshop for a suitable time, such as in November 2025. This event will bring interested stakeholders together to foster connections and co-create ideas for the first intervention phase.

The workshop will be designed to be highly participatory and will motivate stakeholders to develop their own concepts for supporting the challenges. An example agenda for this event would include:

- **Project introduction:** A clear presentation of the project's goals and methodology.
- **Keynote:** A brief, inspiring talk on the importance of the Circular Economy, making connections to the specific city or region
- **Networking and exchange:** An interactive session for stakeholders to introduce themselves, share their work related to the Circular Economy, and articulate their vision for a circular region.
- **Collaborative group work:** Facilitated group sessions to explore how each stakeholder's work relates to the project. The groups will collaboratively brainstorm concrete ideas for activities or offers that could be provided to participating households. The aim is to identify synergies and opportunities for cross-stakeholder collaboration.

The goal is to involve stakeholders representing all four material streams (food, textiles, packaging, and electronics). An example for a successful outcome would be a list of 10-20 concrete ideas for stakeholder-led activities, such as a special discount at a local second-hand shop, a workshop on mending clothes, or a food-sharing initiative. While these activities will be funded and managed by the stakeholders themselves, the project's role is to facilitate their implementation by providing non-monetary support, such as access to rooms or equipment as feasible within each case study. These activities will be locally tailored to directly support the project's core challenges and make it easier for households to implement circular strategies.

3.3.2 Second stakeholder workshop: Visioning and upscaling

The second workshop will be scheduled by each consortium partner towards the end of the first intervention phase or between the two phases, allowing for a flexible timeline based on local needs. Its agenda will focus on feedback, visioning, and planning for upscaling. Key elements will include:

- **Project outlook:** What has happened so far?
- **Review and feedback:** Gaining conceptual feedback from stakeholders on the project's design and execution based on their experience during the first intervention phase.
- **Visioning session:** A collaborative session to envision a "Circular City" or "Circular Region". This will help stakeholders identify new opportunities for a collective circular infrastructure.
- **Concrete planning:** Brainstorming how stakeholders can further get involved. This will include encouraging them to **co-design new challenges** or to **design and integrate circular opportunities** for the second intervention phase, either through expanding their own initiatives, collaborating with others, or contributing new offers.

3.3.3 Workshop evaluation

Workshop evaluation will be a critical part of ensuring the effectiveness of our stakeholder engagement. Immediately following each workshop, participants will be asked to complete a short, anonymous questionnaire to provide feedback. This will allow us to assess key aspects of the event and make improvements for future activities.

The questionnaire, provided in Appendix A, will cover the following areas:

- **Experience and expertise:** Current level of involvement in the Circular Economy
- **Logistics:** Was the workshop well-organised in terms of timing, location, and materials?
- **Engagement:** How effective were the participatory sessions and discussions in facilitating interaction and idea generation?
- **Next steps:** What key actions or collaborations do participants plan to pursue as a direct result of the workshop?

The results of these evaluations will be summarised in a brief **Workshop Summary Documentation**. This will include

- a list of participating stakeholders,
- the captured topics,
- workshop outcomes, including a list of activities and circular opportunities planned by stakeholders for the current upcoming intervention phase,
- photos of the group work outcomes (e.g. flip charts),
- additional photos, such as a group picture of participating stakeholders,
- stakeholder feedback from the evaluation questionnaire and optional notes with further informal feedback.

This documentation will inform future event planning and help to ensure that our engagement strategy remains dynamic and responsive to the needs of our stakeholders.

3.4 Sustaining stakeholder engagement

Keeping stakeholders engaged between workshops and throughout the project is a significant challenge. To address this, a successful strategy will likely employ a mix of proactive communication, platform-based interaction, and personalised outreach. While local partners have the flexibility to determine their specific approach, effective engagement mechanisms include:

- **Regular communications:** Consistently keeping stakeholders informed through dedicated newsletters, social media channels, or a project website to maintain interest and momentum.
- **Digital platform:** Enabling stakeholders to share information and maintain visibility for participants and other partners on the project's digital platform, fostering a sense of community and direct involvement.

In addition to these ongoing communication efforts, a deeper level of personal connection and qualitative insight is highly recommended but remains optional and non-contractual, as this activity is not funded or explicitly detailed within the official grant agreement. If feasible, brief qualitative interviews with selected stakeholders (see Appendix for a guideline) will serve to explore in more depth whether stakeholders have cognitively reframed their existing work through a Circular Economy lens and if the project's activities have influenced their understanding of CE principles. This provides valuable insights beyond what is captured in workshops.

4. Outlook

This stakeholder engagement framework has been designed to strengthen existing local networks and foster new connections across four distinct sociopolitical and geographical contexts: Wantage, Bottrop, Bergen and rural Latvia. The strategy is built on a hybrid approach, leveraging the collective benefits of workshops alongside targeted bilateral communication and optional qualitative exchanges. Insights gained from these activities, and from the involvement of partners on the digital platform, will provide valuable feedback for the project and furthering the core objective of active stakeholder involvement. The goal is for the relationships and momentum initiated during CircleUp to be a starting point, helping to support the diffusion of circular practices throughout the project's duration and beyond.

Next steps for implementation

The next immediate steps focus on transitioning from the strategic planning framework to executing Phase 1 (July–December 2025). Implementing partners must first identify and map stakeholders through local research, then define their tailored communication channels and materials for the first wave of outreach. At the same time, partners should prepare the specific content and logistics for the initial stakeholder workshop. This work will ensure that the groundwork is in place for the first intervention phase to launch smoothly and effectively.

Appendix

Workshop Evaluation questionnaire

This questionnaire was internally developed by the consortium to specifically assess stakeholder engagement within the CircleUp project methodology.

Workshop Feedback: Your Role in the Circular Economy

Thank you for participating in our CircleUp workshop. We designed this event to be a collaborative space, and your input is vital. This short questionnaire will help us understand your current engagement and how we can best support your work in the Circular Economy.

1. Your Experience and Expertise

To better understand your perspective, please tell us about your current level of involvement.

- How would you describe your or your organization's current engagement with the Circular Economy?
 - We are just starting to learn about it.
 - We have some initiatives in place.
 - We are actively and strategically involved.
 - We are a leader in this field.
- In what ways are you or your organization currently involved in the Circular Economy? *(Check all that apply)*
 - Waste reduction/recycling
 - Product design for durability/repair
 - Second-hand/reuse models
 - Skill-sharing or educational events
 - Policy or advocacy work
 - Other (please specify):
- In which material streams are you or your organization currently involved? *(Check all that apply)*
 - Food
 - Textiles
 - Packaging
 - Electronics
 - Other (please specify):
- On a scale of 1 to 5, how confident are you in your ability to contribute to the local Circular Economy?
 - 1 (Not confident) - 2 - 3 (Moderately confident) - 4 - 5 (Very confident)

2. Networking and Collaboration

On a scale of 1 to 5, how confident are you in your ability to contribute to the local Circular Economy?

Standard agreement scale: 1 Strongly disagree / 2 Disagree / 3 Neutral / 4 Agree / 5 Strongly agree

- The workshop provided a good platform for me to connect with other stakeholders.
- I feel that my ideas and contributions were valued during the discussions.
- The group activities successfully encouraged me to think about new ways to collaborate with others.

3. Logistics and Organization

Please provide your feedback on the practical aspects of the workshop.

Standard agreement scale: 1 Strongly disagree / 2 Disagree / 3 Neutral / 4 Agree / 5 Strongly agree

- The workshop's overall duration was appropriate.
- The workshop's schedule and timing were well-managed.
- The venue and its facilities were suitable for the event.
- The provided materials (e.g., handouts, presentation slides) were helpful.
- The registration and pre-workshop communication were clear and effective.

4. Next steps

Your feedback here will directly inform our next steps and help us plan future events.

- After this workshop, how likely are you to get more involved in the CircleUp project?
 - 1 Not likely at all / 2 Not likely / 3 Neutral / 4 Likely / 5 Very likely
- What kind of support would be most helpful for you or your organization to take the next step in your Circular Economy efforts? *(Check all that apply)*
 - More networking opportunities
 - Access to resources/tools/methods
 - Help with communication and promotion
 - Other (please specify):
- Any other suggestions for improving our future workshops or project activities?
(Open-ended text box)

Qualitative Interview Guide: Stakeholder Impact Assessment

This guideline for optional interviews aims to explore the impact of the CircleUp project on stakeholder's perspective and practices. The questions can be chosen or adapted according to the context and interests of the interviewer and interviewee.

1. Awareness and Understanding

- Before participating in CircleUp, how would you have described the Circular Economy? How has your understanding changed since then?
- Do you feel more confident explaining CE principles to others in your organization or network now? Can you give me an example of how that's shown in your work? (Reformulated question)
- How have CircleUp's activities influenced your view of your own role within the broader CE ecosystem?

2. Cognitive Reframing

This section focuses on whether your perspective on your organization's existing offerings has shifted.

- Since joining CircleUp, have you started to view any of your existing products, services, or activities through a new, more circular lens? Which ones and why?
- Can you share an example of how your participation in the project helped you understand how your current offerings contribute to resource efficiency or reuse?
- Before CircleUp, had you considered your work to be part of the Circular Economy? What changed that perspective?

3. Concrete Adaptations

- Have you modified any of your products, services, or communication strategies to align more closely with CE principles since joining CircleUp? If yes, can you describe these changes in more detail?
- Have you introduced any new CE-aligned products or services? If so, what were they and what inspired their development?
- What was the most significant change you made based on insights gained from the CircleUp project?

4. Perceived Influence of CircleUp

- To what extent was your participation in CircleUp a key motivator for the changes you've implemented?
- Thinking about the changes we've discussed, would they have happened without your involvement in CircleUp?
- How has the CircleUp community and its resources – such as the workshops, online platform, or networking—supported your organization's efforts to become more circular?

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